

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7264460>

Abstract. Basically, Teaching must include two major components sending and receiving information. Ultimately, a teacher tries his best to impart knowledge as the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education, but also to empower people, strengthen governance and galvanize the effort to achieve the human development goal for the country with a number of educational options available before the present generation learners, the newer trends seem to have emerged in the field of education that have entirely changed the face of traditional system of education.

Recent trends, methodologies and developments portray the vital role of education sector in general with its internalization of the education process, stress on quality above quantity, increase in the adoption of technologies, necessity for professional talent etc. The theories and methods are constantly evolving in the field of ELT also. This paper presents the famous trends in the ELT that have been used practically in recent times in the entire world with specific reference to the trends prevalent during the previous decades. The study of classical Latin and analysis of its grammar becomes the model from foreign languages in school and this methods and approaches, new trends to foreign language teaching become known as GTM to communicative method.

Keywords: New devices, Methods, ICT, pedagogy, learning process, Approach, Cooperative learning, Suggestopedia.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. По существу, обучение должно включать в себя два основных компонента: отправку и получение информации. В конечном счете, учитель старается передать знания такими, какими он их понял. Использование инновационных методов в образовательных учреждениях может не только улучшить образование, но и расширить возможности людей, укрепить управление и активизировать усилия по достижению цели развития человеческого потенциала в стране благодаря ряду образовательных возможностей, доступных нынешнему поколению учащихся. Похоже, что в сфере образования появились новые тенденции, которые полностью изменили лицо традиционной системы образования.

Последние тенденции, методологии и разработки отражают жизненно важную роль сектора образования в целом с его интернализацией образовательного процесса, упором на качество выше количества, расширением внедрения технологий, потребностью в профессиональных талантах и т. д. Теории и методы постоянно развиваются в области ELT также. В этой статье представлены известные тенденции в ELT, которые использовались практически в последнее время во всем мире, с конкретной ссылкой на тенденции, преобладавшие в предыдущие десятилетия. Изучение классической латыни и анализ ее грамматики становится образцом от иностранных языков в школе, и эти методы и подходы, новые тенденции в обучении иностранным языкам становятся известными как GTM коммуникативному методу.

Ключевые слова: *новые устройства, методы, ИКТ, педагогика, учебный процесс, подход, кооперативное обучение, суггестопедия.*

INTRODUCTION

The innovation that the researcher talks in the paper certain both to methodology and materials used in language teaching. Moreover, this article brings out the subtle distinction between the scholarly perception of language as treated in research and pedagogy. The argument advances as the paper proceeds with trends of education with specific reference to the Indian scenario, methodologies adopted, the bygone methods, the peer practice, the present trend, new teaching design, new devices, the need for change, the ICT and English language. English language teaching has undergone tremendous changes over the years, especially the last ten years.

Students are burdened with studying, learning and grasping the materials, and of course, lectures with the collections of relevant information from prescribed texts. Many career alternatives once regarded insignificant are gaining importance at present such as communication skills, soft skills, technical skills, interpersonal skills, ICT literacy etc. The need for chiseled graduates to merge successfully in the tough competition of survival in the global market is in great demand nowadays. For this, a change in the trend especially the teaching learning process of English language has to undergo a transition for the betterment. Seasons change, fashions changes, attitudes of human beings change but it is disheartening to note that in the last century English curriculum has hardly undergone any change. There had been much of changes in the attitude of people as to what they perceive to be a language. Rigid curriculums and huge syllabi continue to threaten students who speak regional dialect but love to excel in English. The history of foreign language has always been an important practical concern. It was Latin which dominates various fields like education, commerce, religion and government in the western world. In 16th Century French, Italian and English achieve lot of importance as result of political changes in Europe. As the status of Latin language from that of living language to teaching subject in school curriculum. The study of classical Latin and analysis of its grammar becomes the model from Foreign Languages study from 17th to 19th century. In 21st Century we are going to teach communicative language teaching.

According to Kripa K Gautam, “English Language Teaching” - A critical study of methods and approaches have provided account of history of language teaching methods. Methodologies Adapted in Earlier days Communication is the groundwork based on which any idea can progress and develop into a fully fledged one. Without that, sustenance in any field is impossible. During the last decade, various crucial factors have combined to affect the current ideologies of teaching of English such as the ineffective methodologies, unsuitable materials, and integration of contextualized teaching, over emphasis on multi language skills etc. Teachers who practiced Grammar Translation method during the previous decade solely relied on black board as the apt tool to impart communication skills and the nuances of English language. Later on, over head projectors, acted as another medium for the teacher dominated class room. Such teachers believed in the dictum of drill and practice. Researchers had given more emphasis on authentic and meaningful contextualized discourse. Then they focused on a successful adult second language learning as a parallel process to a child’s first language acquisition. With the advent of ecommunication, it has been made possible for the English language teachers to enrich

their profession. Basically, the teacher controls the instructional process, the content is delivered to the entire class and the teacher tends to emphasize factual knowledge. In other words, the teachers deliver the lecture content and the students listen to the lecture.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Thus, the learning mode trends to be passive and the learners play little part in their learning process. It has been found in most universities by many teachers and students that the conventional lecture approach in classroom is of limited effectiveness in both teaching and learning. This method had stayed in practice for a good period of time due to its focus on the functional use of English. But, still this method was marred with setbacks like there were many issues with this method. It needed a lot of time, good budget and a small class size. And even in some situations, it was not very useful. These issues led to another Method that is called Audio-Lingual Method. The direct method is natural method of teaching foreign language its makes use of Audio-Visual Aids. The direct method originated in France in 1801. The direct method develops as a reaction against GTM. Its basic principle is that pupils should think directly in foreign language. DM is to teach language directly at aims to create direct bond between the word and meaning, thought and expression. It's also improving the pupil's pronunciation. In 21st Century there is rise of communicative methodology. Which emphasize real meaning communication method than activity, topic and situations which are artificial and remote from pupil's lies.

Modern Trends of Teaching English

The process of English communication learning will be more student-centered but less time consuming. Therefore, it promises that the teaching quality will be improved and students' applied English communication can be effectively cultivated, meaning that students' communicative competence will be further developed. Language in education would ideally and ordinarily build on such naturally acquired language ability, enriching it through the development of literacy into an instrument for abstract thought and the acquisition of academic knowledge. Teachers use a range of local texts or English translation of literature in the classroom. The use of language as well as the use of a variety of accents in listening activities or tests is encouraged in the English language classroom. With the proliferation of tablets and smart phones, it is believed that textbooks will disappear in a few years. Furthermore, the access to knowledge in terms of flexibility and mobility has changed drastically. Teaching in English language classes focuses on fostering the students thinking as well as language content, outcomes and learning activities. There are significant and complex student-teacher interactions inside and outside the classroom. In a knowledge based society and to remain competitive and employable, teachers are expected to engage in a continuous professional development or the professional learning activities from the beginning to the end of their careers. As with any other profession, teachers are also expected to assume a greater responsibility for their own professional learning, continually developing their knowledge and skills.

Having realized the need of the hour: the English teachers convene different types of conferences and seminars to create a platform and to get to know the upcoming ideologies in the ELT and also to upgrade themselves professionally. It is the fifth skills of language that enables the efficiency to use grammatical structures with accuracy. Academic qualification alone may not help teachers to grow professionally, on the other hand, they need to be equipped themselves with the current practices. The teaching materials that are being used in our country are almost

made available all over the world. There had been too many methodologies of teaching English language. The third dimension of globalization which is inseparable from English teaching is an advancement of Information and Communication Technology. New trends in English language teaching like interactive approach of teaching English is develop as a result of sustain research by the central board of secondary education (CBSE New Delhi). This approach also recommended by the Indian Council of School Education (ICSE New Delhi). To interact means to communicate which each other during interaction. Its means give the information, thoughts unknown to receiver. "Interacting Approach it related to the actual use of language". So interactive teaching styles are Brain Storming, Think pair and share, Buzz session, incident process, Qand A session. In Interactive approach some ideas are follow the leader, Total Physical Response (TPR), One word, Opposite Arguments, Test Tournaments, YouTube Videos Quizzes, Electronic Role Playing, Puzzle pieces.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Communicative language teaching (CLT) emphasize on the process of communication rather than the mastery of language. Some time the term functional approach is use for communicative approach or communicative method. Communicative approach based on the concept of 'communicative competence' which originally introduced H D Hymns. In is article on communicative competence published in, "New origins in Linguistics' in 1971. The communicative approach emphasizes real meaningful communication rather than the activity, topic and situation which are artificial and remote from student's lives. According to geeta Nagraj, "The Development of Language Learning from based to meaning based approach". Communicative approach in was three principle 1. Which involve real communication

2. Which involves various activities. 3. Which emphasize that language is meaningful to the learners

Web Based Learning

Web based learning is one of the fastest developing areas. There are thousands of English web based classes that offer trainings for a variety of basic language skills such as Learning, Speaking, Reading and Writing and are made interactive in a variety of ways. Some of the common technologies a available for promotion of education are as follows: The students can correspond with native speakers of the target language using a email by creating a personal email account (g-mail, yahoo, hotmail, etc) which is free.

The students can mail their home work to the teachers concerned and get it corrected in turn. The teacher can also provide revisions, feedback, suggestions for the betterment of very work and send them back. A blog is a personal or professional journal frequently updated for public consumption. The blogs enable uploading and linking the files which is very much suited to serve as on line personal journals for students. Blogging becomes communicative and interactive when participants assume multiple roles in the writing process, as readers/reviewers who respond to other writer's posts, and as writers-readers who, returning to their own posts, react to criticism of their own posts. The readers in turn can comment on what they read, although blogs can be placed in secured environments as well. Every internet service has audio functions, and technological instruments like laptops with cameras. The students could communicate with their teachers and friends who are far away. Likewise, they could very well communicate with the speakers of native language and get their pronunciation checked so as to improve their speaking. Learners can search for new words using dictionary option in the

mobile phones and enrich their vocabulary. They may verify the spelling pronunciations and usage of the specific word they searched for. Moreover, they can use Short Message Service (SMS) to send queries to their instructors and get their doubts cleared. iPods', one of the multimedia devices, enhance to users to generate, deliver, exchange texts, image, audio and video scripts as per the requirement. The teachers send text messages and the students can read and answer to them.

Suggestopedia

Suggestopedia is a teaching method developed by the Bulgarian psychotherapist Dr. Georgi Lozenov. Suggestopedia has been called a pseudoscience. It strongly depends on the trust that students develop towards the method by simply believing that it works. The purpose of suggestopedia is to enhance learning by tapping into the power of suggestion. Suggestopedia is a system for liberation from the 'preliminary negative concept regarding the difficulties in the process of learning'. Suggestopedia is a pedagogic application of suggestion. It helps learners to overcome the feeling that they cannot be successful and remove their mental barriers to learning.

DISCUSSION

This year, the consumer Electronics Show (CES) which was held at Las Vegas, gave a glimpse of groundbreaking devices purely meant for students. These showpieces ranged from 3D printers to smart watches. The youth's requirements are matched by a new age device, be it studies or social media, travel or portability. The media streaming devices like the Google Chromecast and the Roku make group studies become interactive and presentations surprisingly fulfilled. One has to stream the media on to a smart TV using a dongle. Another blessing is the e-reader for the on-the-move generation. The all-new Kindle Paperwhite is a boon. Students can just tuck in the e-reader for easy reference. The portable document scanner like the Doxie Flip Cordless Flatbed Photo and notebook scanner are used to get notes sorted. Other devices like the copy and Olympus which have come with voice recorders can be utilized to record all the English lectures and be played as and when time permits. A Common Framework of Reference for Languages aims to provide a common basis for the elaboration of language syllabuses, curriculum, what learners have to learn, skills they have to develop so as to be able to act effectively. A clear description of the content in terms of linguistic competency, sociolinguistic competency and pragmatic competency constitutes a language. Using descriptor scales, learner's proficiency is measured. Descriptors consist of a series of can-do statements which received a great deal of attention. The learner's involvement and teacher's empowerment are stressed during the teaching and learning processes. The conventional method of teaching wherein the teacher enjoys the monopoly of teaching sometimes even obliterates the pressure of the learners. Role of Modern Teacher Researchers defined the term role as a technical term which originally comes from sociology and refers to the shared expectation of how an individual should behave. Several methodologies have evolved different roles for a language teacher. Richards and Rodgers conceive a teacher's role as a part of design, component of a method. Littlewood conceptualized the role of the teacher as a facilitator of learning, an overseer, a classroom manager, a consultant or adviser and at times a co-communicator with the learners. To Harmer, a teacher plays the role of controller, organizer, assessor, promoter, participant, resource, tutor and observer. Task-Based Language Teaching is the current paradigm; it is basically an offshoot of Communicative Language Teaching. Experimental learning or learning by doing is the main conceptual basis for the TBLT. The TBLT breaks down the barriers of the

traditional classroom, because in the TBLT, the role of the learner is significantly altered. The teacher becomes a true facilitator or learning for the language learners, purely by means of dialogic communication.

The teacher's role is not shunned altogether but is restricted: the teacher is expected to be guide by the side. The role of teachers how will describe as follows:

1. *Facilitator*
2. *Independent participant*
3. *Needs analyst*
4. *Counselor*
5. *Group processing manager*

CONCLUSION

Across the world, information technology is dramatically altering the way student; faculty and staff learn and work. As the demand for technology continues to rise, colleges and universities are moving all sorts of student services, from laundry monitoring to snack delivery online. Technology is also changing the classroom experience. In addition, tablet PCs, compact computer that allow you to write notes directly onto the screen with a special pen, replace the archaic projector. With the tablet technology allow professor to make notes on charts and spreadsheets and send them directly to their student's PCs. The traditional method lays more emphasis on a teacher himself and is teacher centered.

Repetitive practice, mechanical drills and memorization are the hallmarks of the traditional methods. Role of the teacher is to pertain to the long cherished traditional otion that pedagogic principles depend on how articulately a teacher teaches. It is imperative to understand the current trends and evaluative methods of the ELT. The researchers believe that the ore objective of teaching is passing on the information or knowledge to the minds of the students. Any method using computers or modifying the existing conventional chalk-talk method are innovative if they ultimately serve the attainment of core objective of teaching.

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